

Reading Books and Newspapers in the Italian Regions

Between 2005 and 2020 it decreased on average by 9.20% in the Italian regions

Istat-BES calculates the value of the variable identified as "Reading books and newspapers". This is a variable that calculates the percentage of people aged 6 and over who have read at least four books a year (paper books, e-books, online books, audio books) for reasons that are not strictly educational or professional and / or have read newspapers (printed and / or online) at least three times a week on the total of people aged 6 and over.

Ranking of the Italian regions by the value of reading books and newspapers. Trentino-Alto Adige is in first place for the value of reading books and newspapers with a value of 58.10, followed by Friuli-Venezia Giulia with a value of 53.10 and Emilia Romagna with a value of 50.20 units. In the middle of the table there are Sardinia with a value of 45.30 units, followed by Piedmont with a value of 43.90 and Tuscany with an amount of 42.90. Basilicata closes the ranking with a value of 24.80 units, followed by Campania with an amount of 22.00 units and Calabria with an amount of 21.20. Overall, the average reading value of Italian newspapers is equal to an amount of 39.16 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in the reading of books and newspapers between 2005 and 2020. Puglia is in first place for the value of the percentage change in the reading of books and newspapers with a value equal to 7.20% or equal to an amount of 1.80 units, followed by Abruzzo with an amount of 2.59% equal to an amount of 0.90 units and by Molise with an amount of 2.12% equal to an amount of 0.60 units. In the middle of the table there are Piedmont with an amount of -8.73% equal to an amount of -4.20 units, followed by Campania with an amount of -10.20% equal to an amount of -2.50 units and from Trentino-Alto Adige with an amount of -10.48% equal to an amount of -6.80 units. The Marche closes the ranking with an amount of -17.22% equal to a value of -7.20 units, followed by Tuscany with an amount of -19.36% equal to an amount of -10.30 units and Calabria with an amount of -26.64% equal to an amount of -7.70 units. On average, the value of the percentage change in the reading of books and newspapers decreased for the Italian regions between 2005 and 2020 by an amount equal to -9.20% equal to an amount of -4.46 units.

Italian Macro-Regions. The trend of the variable reading of books and newspapers in the Italian macro-regions is analyzed below. In general, we can see that looking at the historical series it is possible to verify that there is a period in which the reading of books and newspapers grows in the macro-regions, i.e. between 2005 and 2010, and a second period in which the reading of books and newspapers decreased significantly. In Northern Italy, the maximum reading of books and newspapers was reached in 2007 with a value of 53.5. Subsequently, between 2007 and 2020, or in the following 13 years, the value of the reading of books and newspapers decreased by an amount equal to -5.9 units or equal to an amount of -11.02%. In Central Italy, the maximum value of reading books and newspapers was reached in 2005 with an amount equal to 49. However, between 2005 and 2020 the value of reading books and newspapers in Central Italy increased by an amount of 49 units up to a value of 40.6 units or a variation equal to an amount of -8.4 units equal to a value of -17.14%. In the South the maximum reading of books and newspapers was reached in 2009 with an amount equal to a value of 31.8 units. Between 2009 and 2020 the reading of books and newspapers in the South decreased from an amount of 31.8 units up to a value of 27 units or equal to an amount of -4.8 units equal to a value of -15.09%. Overall in Italy the value of reading books and newspapers reached

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its maximum in 2010 with an amount equal to 44.4 units. Between 2010 and 2020 the reading value of books and newspapers decreased from an amount of 44.4 units to a value of 39.2 units or a variation equal to an amount of -5.2 units equal to a value of -11.71%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is then carried out. Two different types of clusters are thus identified, namely:

- Cluster 1: Emilia-Romagna, Lombardy, Liguria, Sardinia, Valle d'Aosta, Tuscany, Veneto, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Piedmont, Trentino-Alto Adige, Lazio, Marche;
- Cluster 2: Sicily, Puglia, Basilicata, Calabria, Campania, Molise, Abruzzo.

By calculating the median value of each cluster, it is evident that the reading of books and newspapers in cluster 1-C1 was equal to an amount of 46.2 units, while the median value of reading books and newspapers in Cluster 2- C2 is equal to an amount of 26.8 units. Therefore, the following ordering of clusters derives, namely: $C1 = 46.2 > C2 = 26.8$. From a geographical point of view, the contrast between Central-Northern Italy which has high reading values of books and newspapers and the regions of Southern Italy which have low reading values of books and newspapers is evident.

Network Analysis using the Manhattan distance. Using network analysis optimized with the Manhattan distance, it is possible to verify the presence of complex network structures. Specifically, there is a complex network structure consisting of Tuscany, Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, and Liguria. Particularly:

- Tuscany is connected to Lombardy with a value of 0.39;
- Lombardy is connected to Tuscany with a value of 0.39 and Emilia Romagna with a value of 0.51 units;
- Emilia-Romagna has a connection with Lombardy for a value of 0.51 units and with Liguria for an amount of 0.48 units;
- Liguria has a connection with Emilia-Romagna equal to an amount of 0.48 units.

Furthermore, the presence of a complex relationship between Sicily, Basilicata, Calabria, and Puglia is detected. Particularly:

- Sicily has a connection with Puglia for a value of 0.43 units, with Calabria for an amount of 0.5 units and with Basilicata for an amount of 0.44 units;
- Puglia has a connection with Sicily for an amount equal to 0.43 units and with Basilicata for an amount equal to 0.53 units;
- Basilicata is connected with Sicily for an amount of 0.44 units and with Puglia for an amount of 0.53 units;
- Calabria has a connection with Sicily for an amount of 0.5 units.

The analysis shows that the most connected region is Sicily. Furthermore, it is possible to verify that the two complex network structures detected tend to reverberate the cluster compositions detected using the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient.

Machine Learning and Predictions. A comparison is made below between ten machine learning algorithms for predicting the value of reading books and newspapers. The data was trained with 80% of the available data. The algorithms were compared based on their ability to minimize statistical errors and maximize R-squared. The following ordering of the algorithms is thus determined, that is:

- SGD with a payoff value of 4;
- Gradient Boosting with a payoff value of 8;
- AdaBoost with a payoff value of 12;
- kNN with a payoff value of 17;
- Random Forest with a payoff value of 19;
- Tree with a payoff value of 24;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 28;
- SVM with a payoff value of 32;

- Constant with a payoff value of 36;
- Neural Network with a payoff value of 40.

Therefore, through the use of the best performer algorithm that the SGD, it is possible to predict the trend of reading books and newspapers for the Italian regions. The SGD algorithm predicts a growth in the reading of books and newspapers for the following regions, namely:

- Calabria with a variation from an amount of 21.20 units up to a value of 25.81 units or equal to an amount of 4.61 units equal to an amount of 21.75%;
- Marche with a change from an amount of 34.60 units up to a value of 38.58 units or equal to a value of 3.98 units equal to an amount of 11.50%;
- Campania with a variation from an amount of 22.00 units up to a value of 23.52 units or equal to an amount of 1.52 units equal to a value of 6.91%;
- Tuscany with a variation from an amount of 42.90 units up to a value of 45.85 units or equal to an amount of 2.95 units equal to a value of 6.88%;
- Sardinia with a variation from an amount of 45.30 units up to a value of 48.06 units or equal to an amount of 2.76 units equal to a value of 6.09%;
- Valle d'Aosta with a variation from an amount of 48.40 units up to a value of 49.93 units or equal to an amount of 1.53 units equal to an amount of 3.16%.

Furthermore, using the SGD algorithm it is possible to predict a negative trend for the following regions, namely:

- Piedmont with a negative change from an amount of 43.90 units up to a value of 43.46 units or equal to an amount of -0.44 units equal to a value of -1.00%;
- Lazio with a negative change from an amount of 41.00 units up to a value of 40.58 units or equal to a value of -0.42 units equal to an amount of -1.02%;
- Liguria with a negative change from an amount of 48.60 units up to a value of 48.10 units or equal to an amount of -0.50 units equal to a value of -1.03%;
- Friuli-Venezia Giulia with a negative change from an amount of 53.10 units up to a value of 52.48 units or equal to a value of -0.62 units equal to a value of -1.17%;
- Lombardy with a change from an amount of 46.70 units up to a value of 45.76 units or equal to a value of -0.94 units or equal to a value of -2.01%;
- Molise with a variation from an amount of 28.90 units up to a value of 28.18 units equal to a variation of -0.72 units equal to a value of -2.49%;
- Basilicata with a variation from an amount of 24.80 units up to a value of 24.18 units or equal to a variation of -0.62 units equal to an amount of -2.50%;
- Umbria with a variation from an amount of 37.90 units up to a value of 36.90 units equal to a variation of -1.00 units equal to an amount of -2.64%;
- Trentino-Alto Adige with a variation from 58.10 units up to a value of 56.44 units or equal to an amount of -1.66 units or equal to a variation of -2.86%;
- Veneto with a variation from an amount of 46.20 units up to a value of 44.70 units equal to an amount of -1.50 units equal to a value of -3.25%;
- Puglia with a variation from an amount of 26.80 units up to a value of 25.52 units or equal to a value of -1.28 units equal to a value of -4.78%;
- Emilia-Romagna with a change from an amount of 50.20 units up to a value of 47.02 units or equal to an amount of -3.18 units equal to an amount of -6.33%;
- Sicily with a variation from an amount of 26.80 units up to a value of 24.38 units or equal to an amount of -2.42 units equal to a value of -9.03%;
- Abruzzo with a variation from an amount of 35.70 units up to a value of 32.39 units or equal to a value of -3.31 units or equal to a value of -9.27%.

Overall, the average value of the prediction for the Italian regions is predicted to decrease by an amount equal to -0.06 units equivalent to a value of -0.16%, passing from an amount of 39.16 units up to a value of 39.09. unit.

Conclusions. The value of reading books and newspapers significantly decreased between 2005 and 2020 in all Italian regions. This reduction is certainly to be associated with the 2007 economic crisis. The economic crisis has also generated a cultural crisis that has hit Italians in all macro-regions. However, it must be considered that in any case there are significant differences between Southern Italy and Central-Northern Italy. The trend of the variable reading of books and newspapers therefore clearly shows the presence of a positive relationship with the gross domestic product. Obviously, in the event of an economic crisis, people are likely to have fewer resources to devote to reading books and newspapers. From this relationship it is also possible to identify a market trend for the publishing sector. In any case, a paradoxical situation arises: in fact in the knowledge economy the skills of reading and understanding texts are very relevant especially in the context of problem solving applied to complexity. However, precisely during a crisis when there is a greater need for production, people have less incentives to increase the reading of books and newspapers, losing cognitive ability and therefore those cognitive skills that are also very relevant for the exercise of work and professional activities in public organizations and private. It is therefore necessary to create incentives for reading, especially in the adverse phases of the economic cycle.

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			Top Valore-20202		
	Top valore		2020	Var Ass	Var Per
Nord	2007	53,5	47,6	-5,9	-11,028
Centro	2005	49	40,6	-8,4	-17,143
Mezzogiorno	2009	31,8	27	-4,8	-15,094
Italia	2010	44,4	39,2	-5,2	-11,712

C1>C2

	2020	Feature 1	SGD
1	43.9	Piemonte	43.4622
2	21.2	Calabria	25.8197
3	26.8	Puglia	25.5293
4	48.4	Valle d'Aosta/V...	49.9322
5	42.9	Toscana	45.8544
6	46.2	Veneto	44.7082
7	41.0	Lazio	40.5843
8	46.7	Lombardia	45.7694
9	26.8	Sicilia	24.3822
10	24.8	Basilicata	24.1805
11	28.9	Molise	28.1853
12	48.6	Liguria	48.1054
13	37.9	Umbria	36.905
14	45.3	Sardegna	48.0682
15	58.1	Trentino-Alto A...	56.4479
16	35.7	Abruzzo	32.3953
17	50.2	Emilia-Romagna	47.0248
18	34.6	Marche	38.5828
19	22.0	Campania	23.5286
20	53.1	Friuli-Venezia G...	52.4882

Predizioni con algoritmo SGD

	2020	SGD	Var Ass	Var Per	
Calabria	21,20	25,81	4,61	21,75	Blue background
Marche	34,60	38,58	3,98	11,50	
Campania	22,00	23,52	1,52	6,91	
Toscana	42,90	45,85	2,95	6,88	
Sardegna	45,30	48,06	2,76	6,09	
Valle D'Aosta	48,40	49,93	1,53	3,16	
Media	39,16	39,09	-0,06	-0,16	Red background
Piemonte	43,90	43,46	-0,44	-1,00	
Lazio	41,00	40,58	-0,42	-1,02	
Liguria	48,60	48,10	-0,50	-1,03	
Friuli Venezia Giulia	53,10	52,48	-0,62	-1,17	
Lombardia	46,70	45,76	-0,94	-2,01	
Molise	28,90	28,18	-0,72	-2,49	
Basilicata	24,80	24,18	-0,62	-2,50	
Umbria	37,90	36,90	-1,00	-2,64	
Trentino Alto Adige	58,10	56,44	-1,66	-2,86	
Veneto	46,20	44,70	-1,50	-3,25	
Puglia	26,80	25,52	-1,28	-4,78	
Emilia Romagna	50,20	47,02	-3,18	-6,33	
Sicilia	26,80	24,38	-2,42	-9,03	
Abruzzo	35,70	32,39	-3,31	-9,27	

Risultati delle predizioni con gli algoritmi di Machine Learning

Rank	Model	MSE	Rank	Model	RMSE	Rank	Model	MAE	Rank	Model	R2
1	SGD	0,000000	1	SGD	0,000000	1	SGD	0,000000	1	SGD	1,000000
2	Gradient Boosting	0,006701	2	Gradient Boosting	0,030974	2	Gradient Boosting	0,034733	2	Gradient Boosting	0,993299
3	AdaBoost	0,009086	3	AdaBoost	0,040551	3	AdaBoost	0,049276	3	AdaBoost	0,990914
4	kNN	0,025730	4	kNN	0,095752	4	Random Forest	0,079867	4	kNN	0,974270
5	Random Forest	0,026222	5	Random Forest	0,097167	5	kNN	0,084966	5	Random Forest	0,973778
6	Tree	0,038412	6	Tree	0,129697	6	Tree	0,115861	6	Tree	0,961588
7	Linear Regression	0,070017	7	Linear Regression	0,198856	7	Linear Regression	0,193896	7	Linear Regression	0,929983
8	SVM	0,139452	8	SVM	0,313504	8	SVM	0,277327	8	SVM	0,860548
9	Constant	0,351835	9	Constant	0,551841	9	Constant	0,574368	9	Constant	0,648165
10	Neural Network	1,000000	10	Neural Network	1,000000	10	Neural Network	1,000000	10	Neural Network	0,000000

Lettura di Libri e di Quotidiani																
	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Piemonte	48.1	46.5	50	48.7	52.1	49.3	50	46.2	44.8	44.6	44.1	45.2	41.2	45.1	42.8	43.9
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	58.2	59	56.1	58	52.3	54.6	52	55.5	50.6	49.3	51.6	54.8	47.3	49.1	49	48.4
Liguria	57.3	57.4	53.8	57.6	56.6	54.1	52	50.7	48.5	47.3	48.3	49.3	50.2	50.2	44.2	48.6
Lombardia	54.9	53.9	54.1	52.6	51.8	52	51.7	50	48.1	44.3	46.2	48.6	45	47	44.7	46.7
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	64.9	65	66.1	65.2	66.2	65.4	63.2	62.5	57.9	59.9	60.3	60.3	58	56.2	57.2	58.1
Veneto	47.9	49.4	50.4	48.8	48.8	52.2	51	50.8	47.2	42.8	42.8	47.6	46.5	45	46.5	46.2
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	56.3	56.5	60.2	60.4	59.6	57.7	58.7	56.6	57.1	57.6	56.1	58.7	55.1	53	52	53.1
Emilia-Romagna	52.3	56.3	54.5	53.3	52.9	53.5	50.7	51.8	48.1	49	46.8	50	49.1	49.9	45.8	50.2
Toscana	53.2	51.5	54.7	50.1	50.3	53.4	51.3	47.4	44.7	44.3	47.5	47.2	43	47.5	44.7	42.9
Umbria	43.3	41.3	41.8	42.7	39.5	39.8	38.8	38	35.1	36.5	41.9	41	36.8	35.4	36.6	37.9
Marche	41.8	42.7	42.9	40.7	43.3	41.6	39.4	40.2	39.3	37.3	38.5	40.7	38.7	39.6	39	34.6
Lazio	49.2	46.3	46.7	48.4	46	47.8	44.9	43.2	39.4	40.5	37.5	42.6	40.1	38.5	39.1	41
Abruzzo	34.8	33.2	34.1	35.5	38.8	36.2	37.1	38.4	32.4	31.4	29.9	36.8	31.8	31.7	35.5	35.7
Molise	28.3	28.9	30.7	28.8	30.8	29.3	28.1	26.7	27	29.1	25.4	31.4	29.4	31	27.9	28.9
Campania	24.5	26.6	26	24.9	28.7	27.1	25.6	22.1	21	21.2	21.1	23.8	20.6	21.4	21.4	22
Puglia	25	31.1	26.6	24.5	29.3	30.4	27.4	26.9	23.8	24.1	23.6	26.8	24	25.3	26.4	26.8
Basilicata	25.1	28.5	27.4	26.6	25.6	26.1	25.1	24.9	23	20.8	21.9	24.4	23.9	27.1	24.3	24.8
Calabria	28.9	26.7	25	26.6	29.4	29	26	28.3	23.1	23.3	21	21.5	21.5	22.1	23.8	21.2
Sicilia	27.1	28.2	27.6	28.1	29.3	28.7	25.6	26.1	21.9	21.7	25.4	26.1	23.1	24.1	24.2	26.8
Sardegna	51.3	52	51.5	52.7	55.7	55.9	57.8	49.8	50.2	49.9	49.1	51.5	48.2	48.3	45	45.3

**Variazione percentuale della Lettura dei Libri e dei
Quotidiani tra il 2005 ed il 2020**

Rank	Regione	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 1,80	★ 7,20
2	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 0,90	★ 2,59
3	<i>Molise</i>	★ 0,60	★ 2,12
4	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ -0,30	★ -1,11
5	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ -0,30	★ -1,20
6	<i>Veneto</i>	★ -1,70	★ -3,55
7	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ -2,10	★ -4,02
8	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ -3,20	★ -5,68
9	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ -4,20	★ -8,73
10	<i>Campania</i>	★ -2,50	★ -10,20
11	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	★ -6,80	★ -10,48
12	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ -6,00	★ -11,70
13	<i>Umbria</i>	★ -5,40	★ -12,47
14	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ -8,20	★ -14,94
15	<i>Liguria</i>	★ -8,70	★ -15,18
16	<i>Lazio</i>	★ -8,20	★ -16,67
17	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	★ -9,80	★ -16,84
18	<i>Marche</i>	★ -7,20	★ -17,22
19	<i>Toscana</i>	★ -10,30	★ -19,36
20	<i>Calabria</i>	★ -7,70	★ -26,64
	<i>Media</i>	★ -4,465	★ -9,2

Lettura di Libri e Quotidiani	
Regioni	2020
<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	★ 58,10
<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ 53,10
<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 50,20
<i>Liguria</i>	★ 48,60
<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	★ 48,40
<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 46,70
<i>Veneto</i>	★ 46,20
<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 45,30
<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 43,90
<i>Toscana</i>	★ 42,90
<i>Lazio</i>	★ 41,00
<i>Umbria</i>	★ 37,90
<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 35,70
<i>Marche</i>	★ 34,60
<i>Molise</i>	★ 28,90
<i>Puglia</i>	★ 26,80
<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 26,80
<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 24,80
<i>Campania</i>	★ 22,00
<i>Calabria</i>	★ 21,20
<i>Media</i>	★ 39,16

Lettura di Libri e Quotidiani nel 2020

Variazione assoluta della Lettura dei Libri e dei Quotidiani tra il 2005 ed il 2020

Variazione percentuale della Lettura dei Libri e dei Quotidiani tra il 2005 ed il 2020

